

ilar set of varieties was sown 17 Jul 1982 and their performance was compared to that of the ratooned crop.

Plant height, panicle length, and tiller number were higher for ratoons than for

normal sown man rice. Ratooned Tillakachari and Achra 108/1 yielded more than the aman sowing of the same varieties (see table). The mean yield of ratooned rice varieties equaled that of

normal sown rice, indicating the suitability of ratoon cultivation in lowland areas where flood or sudden water stagnation hampers the freshly planted rice crop during the wet season. □

Fungi-caused rotten disease of azolla

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In 1981, the fungus *Myrothecium* sp. was discovered to cause rotten disease of azolla. In 1982 azolla propagation in north-east Thailand was increased and an outbreak of rotten disease occurred. Damage was more severe than in 1981 and symptoms were different from those caused by *Myrothecium* sp. Disease samples were collected from a farmer's propagation pond in Sakolnakorn Province in Nov-Dec 1982. Six genera of fungi were isolated: *Myrothecium* sp., *Rhizoctonia* sp., *Sclerotium* sp., *Fusarium* sp., and two unidentified fungi. One unidentified genus had a yellow colony of mycelium, the other a black colony. All were grown on potato dextrose agar.

Healthy azolla was individually inoculated with the six isolated fungi and grown in a 38-cm-diameter pot. Each

Comparison of disease symptom development on *Azolla pinnata* after inoculation by selected fungi.

Fungus	Symptom development, (days after inoculation)			Azolla death (days after inoculation)	Azolla rotting (days after inoculation)	Disease appearance
	Leaf	Stem	Root			
<i>Rhizoctonia</i> sp.	2	2	2	3-4	5-7	Infected fern turned pale-brown in color, then brown to dark brown.
<i>Myrothecium</i> sp.	2	2	3	3-5	10-15	Infected fern turned grey-green in color, then grey-brown to dark brown.
<i>Sclerotium</i> sp.	7	-	-	-	-	Infected fern showed only small brown lesion on leaf.
<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	-	-	-	-	-	No symptom
Unidentified (yellow colony)	-	-	-	-	-	No symptom
Unidentified (black colony)	-	-	-	-	-	No symptom
Distilled water (control)	-	-	-	-	-	No symptom

treatment and a distilled water sprayed control was replicated four times. Disease development was recorded.

Rhizoctonia sp. damaged azolla most, causing infected ferns to rot 5-7 days after inoculation. *Myrothecium* sp.

caused rotting 10-15 days after inoculation (see table). *Sclerotium* sp. caused small brown lesions on the leaves 7 days after inoculation, but did not cause rotting. *Fusarium* sp. and the two unidentified fungi did not cause the disease. □

Effects of plant population and urea supergranule deep placement on rice yield

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We studied the effect of plant population and deep placement of urea supergranules (USG) on rice yield at Coimbatore in 1980 wet season and 1981 dry season (Jan-May). The soil was clay loam with pH 7.8, 0.38% carbon, and CEC 26.8 meq/100 g.

The trial was laid out in a randomized block design with four planting treatments in five replications. Plot size was .0 × 4.0 m. Heavy tillering rice Co 43 from the cross Dhasal/IR20 was planted

Effect of plant spacing and USG placement on rice panicles and grain yield of Co 43.^a

Spacing (cm)	Hills (no./m ²)	USG (no./4 hills)	Panicles/m ²		Panicle wt (g)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
			WS	DS	WS	DS	WS	DS
15 × 10	66	1	489	476	1.90	1.85	4.9	6.1
15 × 20	33	2	315	586	2.68	2.44	5.2	6.6
22.5 × 20	22	3	233	495	2.85	2.22	5.2	6.3
30 × 20	16	4	225	470	2.39	2.24	5.1	6.2
CD (0.05)	-	-	39	30	0.27	0.48	0.2	0.2

^aUrea supergranule (USG) at 75 kg N/ha was deep placed. WS = wet season, DS = dry season.

at 2 seedlings/hill. The table gives treatment details and number of panicles, panicle weight, and grain yield.

Results indicated that 20 × 15 cm spacing (33 plants/m²), or half the population of conventional spacing, gave significantly higher grain yield in both

seasons. Yield with 22 plants/m² equaled that of 33 plants/m² during wet season. However, yield with 33 plants/m² was significantly higher than with 22 plants/m² during dry season (see table).

The number of panicles/m² was significantly higher in a conventional plant-

ing with 66 hills/m² in wet season, but was higher at 15- × 20-cm spacing in dry season.

Panicle weights from treatments of 33 and 22 hills were comparable in both

seasons. Panicle weight for 66 hills was the lowest.

Deep placement utilizes more labor at conventional spacing. Using the modified 15 × 20 cm spacing reduced the

number of planting sites 50%, and therefore reduced seed and planting costs 50%. These savings will compensate for the extra labor needed for USG deep placement. □

Multiplication of azolla in alkaline soils of Punjab

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Azolla may be a substitute for nitrogen fertilizer in wetland rice, but its multiplication and growth are determined by soils and environmental factors. We studied azolla growth patterns in a subtropical alkaline soil at the PAU farm in Ludhiana.

Six concrete tanks (2 × 2.2 m) were filled to 15 cm with a sandy loam soil with pH 8.4. A 15–20 cm water level above the soil was maintained. Tanks were inoculated with 250 g of a local azolla species in Jun 1979. Superphosphate at 1.75 kg P/ha per week was applied to each tank. The temperature of the top 0-2 cm of water in the tank was recorded daily at 1500 hours. Azolla growth and N fixation were monitored every 2 weeks throughout the year.

Growth rate of azolla in tanks as affected by temperature.

Azolla harvested in Mar, Apr, and Oct weighed 10-13 t fresh matter/ha per month and contained 30 kg N/ha. Fresh matter and total N varied from 0.3 to 4.2 t and 0.8–10.7 kg N/ha per month for other months. Azolla produced 55 t/ha per year, which contained about 139 kg N.

Azolla grew slowly from Jun to Sep, which is the rice season, because of high ambient temperatures (see figure). High standing water temperatures (34–39 °C) from May to Sep and low temperatures (16–21 °C) from Dec to Feb reduced azolla growth. Azolla species with high temperature tolerance need to be tested. □

Rock phosphate-pyrite mixture: a good substitute for single superphosphate

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Use of inexpensive, readily available fertilizers without sacrificing yield is top priority. From kharif 1979 to 1981 we compared yields from neutral and alkaline rice fields fertilized with a basal application of a single superphosphate with those of fields treated with a 1:5 rock phosphate-pyrite mixture. Both treatments received 26.4 kg P/ha.

Trials were conducted at the Regional Research Station at Mandya on a sandy loam Alfisol (pH 6.9, Olsen's P 8.5 kg/ha, and CEC 16.8 meq/100 g) and at the Agricultural Research Station at

Direct and residual effect of rock phosphate-pyrite mixture on grain yield (av of 3 seasons).^a

Treatment	Yield (t/ha) (av 3 seasons)		P uptake in rough rice (kg/ha)		% recovery in rough rice		Olsen's P (kg/ha) after 3 seasons (RRS, Mandya -NS)	Residual effect on grain yield (P treated plot-control) t/ha (RRS, Mandya -NS)
	Mandya (NS)	Siruguppa (HS)	NS	HS	NS	HS		
Control (no P)	4.1	3.6	11.5	7.6	—	—	8.7	—
Single superphosphate at 26.4 kg P/ha	4.9	4.7	15.2	11.8	11.4	15.2	9.4	0.8
Rock phosphate – pyrite mixture (1:5) at 26.4 kg P/ha	5.2	4.9	17.9	13.2	22.7	21.7	12.0	1.1
F Test	*	**						*
CD (0.05)	0.67	0.81						0.48
CV (%)	12.1	10.3						14.6

^aNS = neutral soil, HS = high pH soil.

Siruguppa on a silty clay Vertisol (pH 8.6, Olsen's P 6.2 kg/ha, and CEC 24.2 meq/100 g). Recommended agronomic pro-

cedures were used for the transplanted crops, and Prakash (IET2254) was grown. The Mussoorie rock phosphate used